

Not Distributive Lattice Over Cartesian Residue Classes Modulo Primes

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Abstract:

The concept of almost distributive lattices (ADL) [6] and perfect distributive lattices [10] have been utilized in various fields starting from mathematical logic and the concept of not distributive lattices can be used in coding. Even though the ring of residue classes modulo prime p has no divisors of zero, the polynomial ring that has polynomials with coefficients as n - tuples formed by the Cartesian product of finite fields residue classes modulo primes and this algebra is a polynomial ring using direct sum and direct product, forms a ring with divisors of zero. This helps to create a not distributive lattice over a polynomial ring. The formed lattice will be encrypted using a specific key and with the help of parity digit that will be included into the encrypted message that will be sent through three messages and with a question among these three messages, one message will have the correct parity digit and that will allow the receiver to decrypt the original message. Any hacker will face difficulty due to the not distributive nature of the original algebra abbreviated as NDLOCRCMP.

Key words: Divisors of zero, Euclidean Ring, Direct Sum, Direct Product, degree of the polynomial modulo prime, field, Polynomial ring, partial ordering, ciphering

Literature Review: constructing polynomial rings taking coefficients from different fields or integral domains that are from residue classes modulo composite or primes and searching for the divisors of zero, depending on the existence of the divisors of zero or not will help us to create new algebras or polynomial rings with or without the divisors of zero, upon which the lattices can be constructed that may or may not satisfy the distributive properties. With this perspective, in the present discussion, the carried out work is on constructing a lattice upon a algebra and testing for the failure of the distributive property.

1. Introduction:

A set together with two binary operations $+$ and \times satisfying the following conditions is a ring. $(R, +)$ is an abelian group, (R, \times) is a semi group and distributive laws hold.

..... 1.1

A commutative ring with unity in which every non zero element possess multiplicative inverse is a field.

..... 1.2

If $(F, +, \times)$ is a field and x is an indeterminate, then $F[x]$ is the collection of all polynomials [1] in x also forms a ring under and addition and multiplication of polynomials, is also a ring called the polynomial ring.

..... 1.3

The set of integers is \mathbb{Z} is an integral domain [2] and by taking residues when divided by a prime number p leaves reminders $0, 1, 2, \dots, p - 1$. These reminders form classes that are the elements of \mathbb{Z}_p used to construct a field $(\mathbb{Z}_p, +_p, \times_p)$ with the elements $[0], [1], [2], \dots$,

$[p - 1]$ where $+_p$ is called the addition modulo p and \times_p is the multiplication modulo p .
..... 1.4

$(\mathbb{Z}_p, +_p, \times_p)$ is the set of integers modulo prime number p under addition modulo p and multiplication modulo p is a field. The set of all polynomials over \mathbb{Z}_p form an integral domain and so a polynomial domain. 1.5

A relation \leq on a set L is said to be a partial ordering, if it is reflexive, anti-symmetric and transitive. 1.6

A partial order \leq on a set L together form a partial order set or simply poset (L, \leq) .

A poset (L, \leq) is said to be a lattice if every pair of members a and b of L must be assigned with two operations \vee called join and \wedge called meet satisfying

$$a \vee b = \text{supremum } \{a, b\} \text{ and } a \wedge b = \text{infimum } \{a, b\} \quad \text{..... 1.7}$$

The properties $a \vee a = a, a \wedge a = a, a \vee b = b \Leftrightarrow a \leq b, a \wedge b = b \Leftrightarrow b \leq a, a \vee (b \wedge c) = (a \vee b) \wedge c, a \wedge (b \vee c) = (a \wedge b) \vee c$ hold in a lattice. 1.8

If $a \vee (b \wedge c) = (a \vee b) \wedge (a \vee c)$ & $a \wedge (b \vee c) = (a \wedge b) \vee (a \wedge c)$ for every a, b, c in L holds, then L is a distributive lattice. If at least one between these properties does not hold for at least one triad of elements in L , then L is not a distributive lattice. 1.9

2. Creating a polynomial ring with divisors of zero [4] & [5]

Consider $\mathbb{Z}_{p_1} \times \mathbb{Z}_{p_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{Z}_{p_k} = \Gamma$ 2.1

forms a ring under the direct addition $(+_p, +_p, \dots, +_p) = \oplus_p$ 2.2

and direct multiplication $(\times_{p_1}, \times_{p_2}, \dots, \times_{p_k}) = \odot_p$ 2.3

Consider $(\mathbb{Z}_{p_1} \times \mathbb{Z}_{p_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{Z}_{p_k})[x] = \Gamma[x]$

$$= \{f(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} ([\alpha_{1i}], [\alpha_{2i}], \dots, [\alpha_{ki}])x^{i \bmod p_r} / [\alpha_{si}] \in \mathbb{Z}_{p_s}, 1 \leq s \leq k\}$$

$p_r = \max\{p_i / 1 \leq i \leq k\}$, is a polynomial domain taking the degree of the polynomial as the distance function $d(f(x))$, $(\Gamma[x], \oplus, \odot)$ is a Euclidean ring, where \oplus is defined by

$$f(x) \oplus g(x) =$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^{k-1} ([\alpha_{1i}] +_{p_1} [\beta_{1j}], [\alpha_{2i}] +_{p_2} [\beta_{2j}], \dots, [\alpha_{ki}] +_{p_k} [\beta_{kj}])x^{\max(i,j) \bmod p_r} \text{ and } \odot$$

is defined by $f(x) \odot g(x) =$

$$= \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} (\{[\alpha_{1i}] \times_{p_1} [\beta_{1j}], [\alpha_{2i}] \times_{p_2} [\beta_{2j}], \dots, [\alpha_{ki}] \times_{p_k} [\beta_{kj}]\})x^{(i+j) \bmod p_r} \quad \text{..... 2.4}$$

Observe that $|\Gamma[x]| = p_1 p_2 \dots p_{k-1} p_k^2$ where $\{p_i\}$ is an ascending sequence of primes.

..... 2.5

$$\begin{aligned} \deg(f(x)g(x)) &= \max\{x^{(i+j) \bmod p_r} / 1 \leq i \leq k\} \\ &\leq \max\{x^{i \bmod p_i} / 1 \leq i \leq k\} \cdot \max\{x^{j \bmod p_j} / 1 \leq j \leq k\} \\ &\leq \deg(f(x)) \cdot \deg(g(x)) \end{aligned} \quad \text{..... 2.6}$$

See that if for a particular i , $([0], [0], \dots, [0], [\alpha_{ri}], [0], \dots, [0])x^{i \bmod p_r}$,

$p_r = \max\{p_i / 1 \leq i \leq k\}$ is not the zero element of $\Gamma[x]$ and

$([0], [0], \dots, [0], [\beta_{rj}], [0], \dots, [0])x^j$ is also not equal to

$([0], [0], \dots, [0], [0], [0], \dots, [0])x^{i \bmod p_r}$ in $\Gamma[x]$. However,

$$([0], [0], \dots, [0], [\alpha_{ri}], [0], \dots, [0])x^{i \bmod p_r} \odot_p ([0], [0], \dots, [0], [\beta_{rj}], [0], \dots, [0])x^{j \bmod p_r}$$

$$= ([0], [0], \dots, [0], [0], [0], \dots, [0])x^{(i+j) \bmod p_r} \text{ in } \Gamma[x]$$

This verifies $([0], [0], \dots, [0], [\alpha_{ri}], [0], \dots, [0])x^{i \bmod p_r}$ and

$([0], [0], \dots, [0], [\beta_{tj}], [0], \dots, [0])x^{j \bmod p_r}$ in $\Gamma[x]$ are the divisors of zeros. 2.7

The degree of the polynomial is the non negative integer and p_r is a positive integer, the division algorithm can be verified on the members of $\Gamma[x]$ 2.8

The observations (2.1), through (2.8) satisfy $\Gamma[x]$ is a Euclidean ring. 2.9

3. Creating a lattice over the polynomial ring $\Gamma[x]$ [6], [7], [8]

Let us construct an ordering relation on the members of $\Gamma[x]$ as $f(x) \leq g(x) \Leftrightarrow$

$\alpha_{si} \leq \beta_{sj} \forall 1 \leq s, i \leq k$ where $[\beta_{sj}] = \text{coeff}(g(x))$ and $[\alpha_{si}] = \text{coeff}(f(x))$

$\deg f(x) \leq \deg g(x)$

$f(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1}([\alpha_{1i}], [\alpha_{2i}], \dots, [\alpha_{ki}])x^{i \bmod p_r}$ and $g(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{k-1}([\beta_{1j}], [\beta_{2j}], \dots, [\beta_{kj}])x^{j \bmod p_r}$,

$\alpha_{si} = \beta_{sj} \forall 1 \leq s, i \leq k$ allows $f(x) = g(x)$ leading to antisymmetric and thus, $(\Gamma[x], \leq)$ is a poset. 3.1

p_i is a prime number with which the residue classes modulo p_i are constructed. So, $[1], [2], \dots, [p_i - 1]$ are mutually relatively prime modulo p_i . So,

$$f(x) \vee g(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1}(\{[\alpha_{1i}] +_{p_1} [\beta_{1j}], \{[\alpha_{2i}] +_{p_2} [\beta_{2j}], \dots, \{[\alpha_{ki}] +_{p_k} [\beta_{kj}]\})x^{\max(i,j) \bmod p_r} \quad \dots 3.2$$

$$f(x) \wedge g(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1}(\{[\alpha_{1i}] \times_{p_1} [\beta_{1j}], \{[\alpha_{2i}] \times_{p_2} [\beta_{2j}], \dots, \{[\alpha_{ki}] \times_{p_k} [\beta_{kj}]\})x^{(i+j) \bmod p_r} \quad \dots 3.3$$

(3.2) and (3.3) can show that whenever $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ are in L , it follows $f(x) \vee g(x)$ and $f(x) \wedge g(x)$ are the members of L satisfying (1.6) through (1.9) making $(\Gamma[x], \leq)$ a lattice. 3.4

Theorem: the lattice constructed in (3.1) through (3.4) is not a distributive lattice

Proof: (2.7) has shown that the lattice constructed is having divisors of zero. 3.5

So, let $(x) = ([0], [0], \dots, [0], [\alpha_{ri}], [0], \dots, [0])x^{i \bmod p_r}$,

$g(x) = ([0], [0], \dots, [0], [\beta_{sj}], [0], \dots, [0])x^{i \bmod p_r}$, $s \neq r$ and

$$h(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1}([\gamma_{1i}], [\gamma_{2i}], \dots, [\gamma_{ki}])x^{i \bmod p_r}$$

Consider $f(x) \wedge \{g(x) \vee h(x)\}$

Observe that $g(x) \vee h(x) =$

$$= \sum_{i=0}^{k-1}([0] +_{p_1} [\beta_{1j}], [0] +_{p_2} [\beta_{2j}], \dots, [\alpha_{sj}] +_{p_s} [\beta_{si}], [0] +_{p_{s+1}} [\alpha_{(s+1)j}], \dots, [0] +_{p_k} [\beta_{kj}])x^{\max(i,j) \bmod p_r}$$

$$= \sum_{i=0}^{k-1}([\beta_{1j}], [\beta_{2j}], \dots, [\alpha_{sj}] +_{p_s} [\beta_{si}], \dots, [\beta_{kj}])x^{\max(i,j) \bmod p_r}$$

Using this, $f(x) \wedge \{g(x) \vee h(x)\} =$

$$\sum_{i=0}^{k-1} \left([0] \times_{p_1} \{[0] +_{p_1} [\gamma_{1j}]\}, [0] \times_{p_2} \{[0] +_{p_2} [\gamma_{2j}]\}, \dots, [\alpha_{ri}] \times_{p_i} \{[\beta_{sj}] +_{p_s} [\gamma_{si}]\}, \right. \\ \left. [0] \times_{p_{s+1}} \{[0] +_{p_{s+1}} [\gamma_{(s+1)j}]\}, \dots, [0] \times_{p_k} \{[\beta_{kj}] +_{p_s} [\gamma_{ki}]\} \right) x^{\max(i,j) \bmod p_r}$$

$$= \sum_{i=0}^{k-1}([0], [0], \dots, [\alpha_{ri}] \times_{p_i} \{[\beta_{sj}] +_{p_s} [\gamma_{si}]\}, [0], \dots, [0])x^{\max(i,j) \bmod p_r} \quad \dots 3.6$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & f(x) \wedge g(x) \\
 &= \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} \left(\{ [0] \times_{p_1} [0] \}, \{ [0] \times_{p_2} [0] \}, \dots, [0] \times_{p_r} [\beta_{rj}], [\alpha_{sj}] \times_{p_j} [0], [0], \dots, [0] \right) \\
 & \quad \quad \quad x^{(i+j) \bmod p_r} \\
 &= ([0], [0], \dots, [0], \dots, [0]) \quad \dots 3.7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & f(x) \wedge h(x) \\
 &= \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} \left(\{ [0] \times_{p_1} [\gamma_{1j}] \}, \{ [0] \times_{p_2} [\gamma_{1j}] \}, \dots, [\alpha_{ki}] \times_{p_r} [\gamma_{1j}], [0] \times_{p_1} [\gamma_{1j}], \dots, [0] \right) \\
 & \quad \quad \quad x^{(i+j) \bmod p_r} \\
 &= \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} ([0], [0], \dots, [\alpha_{ki}] \times_{p_r} [\gamma_{1j}], [0], \dots, [0]) x^{(i+j) \bmod p_r} \quad \dots 3.8
 \end{aligned}$$

Using (3.7) and (3.8), $\{f(x) \wedge g(x)\} \vee \{f(x) \wedge h(x)\} = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} ([0], [0], \dots, [\alpha_{ki}] \times_{p_r} [\gamma_{1j}], [0], \dots, [0]) x^{(i+j) \bmod p_r}$ 3.9
 (3.6) \neq (3.9) verifies the said condition.

Similarly,

$$f(x) \vee \{g(x) \wedge h(x)\} = \sum_{t=0}^{k-1} ([0], [0], \dots, [\gamma_{ri}], [0], \dots, [\beta_{sj}] \times_j [\gamma_{tj}], \dots, [0], \dots, [0]) \cdot x^{t \bmod k} \quad \dots 3.10$$

On the other hand, $\{f(x) \wedge g(x)\} \vee \{f(x) \wedge h(x)\} =$

$$\sum_{t=0}^{k-1} ([0], [0], \dots, [\alpha_{ri}] \times_{p_i} \{[\beta_{ri}] +_{p_i} [\gamma_{ti}]\}, [0], \dots, [\alpha_{sj}] \times_j \{[\beta_{rj}] +_{p_i} [\gamma_{tj}]\}, \dots, [0], \dots, [0]) x^{t \bmod k} \quad \dots 3.11$$

(3.10) and (3.11) verifies that join over meet also shows the distributive law fails in $(\Gamma[x], \leq)$.

4. Enciphering/Deciphering the members of lattice $(\Gamma[x], \leq)$

$([\alpha_2], [\alpha_3], \dots, [\alpha_{k+1}]) x^{r \bmod k} \equiv [\beta_2][\beta_3] \dots [\beta_{k+1}]$ in which the integers are concatenated to form a string or text and only remainder integers are exhibited in the text that satisfies $\alpha_i \cdot \beta_i \equiv 1 \bmod p_i, 1 \leq i \leq k$

If a particular $\alpha_j = 0$ in the 2nd to $k+1$ th positions of the string, then the position β_i will be 0 and the location $k + i + 1$ will be p_i for $1 \leq i \leq k$ 4.1

In view of (2.5), we can construct $2k + 1$ length strings following this pattern.

The 1st place in the string β_1 will be $r \bmod k$ which is the degree of the polynomial $x^{r \bmod k}$ 4.2

The encoded string due to concatenation is $\beta_1 \beta_2 \dots \beta_{2k+1}$ 4.3

While deciphering, the location of β_i where $2 \leq i \leq k + 1$ will be replaced by α_i with the same relation $\beta_i \cdot \alpha_i \equiv 1 \bmod p_i$. If a particular location $i, 2 \leq i \leq k + 1$ is 0, then it will be replaced by the bit in the same location $k + 1 + i, 1 \leq i \leq k$.

Pulling the 1st location of the string due to cipher text to the degree of the polynomial $x^{\beta_1} = x^{r \bmod k}$.

The deciphered string is, $\alpha_2 \dots \alpha_{k+1} \alpha_1 00 \dots 0 \equiv ([\alpha_2], [\alpha_3], \dots, [\alpha_{k+1}]) x^{r \bmod k}$

The method of enciphering is a critical job while which primes are used in creating the algebra and the following lattice are not known. So, breaking the enciphering procedure itself cannot be identified. If it done, the deciphering is trivial. The parity digit will be the degree of the polynomial written at the beginning of the code.

5. Outcome

The lattice $(\Gamma[x], \leq)$ is verified to be **Not Distributive Lattice Over Cartesian Residue Classes Modulo Primes** or simply **NDLOCRCMP**. This algebra is useful in coding and can give tough deal for the hackers while there are multiple choices for the right hand side of the distributive property.

Scope: the motive of creating not distributive lattice over a polynomial ring is absolutely useful to the coding with a perspective of artificial intelligence, search engines and escape from hackers. The other direction in which the above discussion can be taken mathematically into norm of the polynomial or function in the said polynomial ring $\Gamma[x]$. The coefficients of the polynomials can be taken from different algebras including matrices so that the Holder and Minkowski equalities help to establish the not distributive nature of the possible lattice in the ring $\Gamma[x]$.

References:

1. https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Lattices_over_Polynomial_Rings_and_Applications_to_Function_Fields
2. [Algebraic lattices via polynomial rings | Computational and Applied Mathematics](https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40314-019-0948-8)
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40314-019-0948-8>
3. Not Distributive Lattice Over a Field of Residue classes modulo 5. *IJERT*.
<https://www.ijert.org>, Vol.9, Issue:5, 2020
4. [Finitely Generated Abelian Groups as Unions of Proper Subgroups on JSTOR](https://www.jstor.org/stable/2371833)
Azriel Rosenfeld, *The American Mathematical Monthly*, Vol. 70, No. 10 (Dec., 1963), pp. 1070-1074 (5 pages), published By: Taylor & Francis, Ltd.
5. Abelian groups that are direct summands of every containing abelian group1, R.Baer, 1940, projecteuclid.org
6. Swamy UM, Rao GC. Almost distributive lattices. *Journal of the Australian Mathematical Society Series A Pure Mathematics and Statistics*. 1981;31(1):77-91. doi:10.1017/S1446788700018498
7. T.S.R., & L, S. (2019).Residue Matrix and not Distributive Lattice. *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology, 67*(8), 1-3.
<https://doi.org/10.14445/22315373/IJMTT-V65I8P501>
@article{srinivasarao55not, title={Not Distributive Lattice Over Residue Classes Polynomial Ring},author={Srinivasarao, T and Ashok,},journal={rn}, volume={55, Pages={7}}
8. Srinivasarao, T., & Ashok, G. Not Distributive Lattice Over Residue Classes Polynomial Ring. *rn*, 55, 7.
@article{srinivasarao55not, title={Not Distributive Lattice Over Residue Classes Polynomial Ring},author={Srinivasarao, T and Ashok, G},journal={rn}, volume={55}, pages={7}}
9. Srinivasarao, T., & Lakshmi, K. G. Not Distributive Lattice Over a Galois Field. *rn*, 55, 7.

@article{srinivasarao55not, title={Not Distributive Lattice Over a Galois Field}, author={Srinivasarao, T and Lakshmi, K Geetha}, journal={rn}, volume={55}, pages={7}}

10. Perfect Distributive Lattices
chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/<https://math.bme.hu/~schmidt/papers/54.pdf>
11. <https://www.ijert.org/not-distributive-lattice-over-field-of-residue-classes-modulo-5>
papered:IJERTV915050038, Vol.9, Issue:5

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